

SPECIFICITY OF THE ADVANTAGES OF ENDOSCOPIC AND CONVENTIONAL SURGICAL INTERVENTIONS IN THE BILIARY TRACT

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Relevance. In this regard, as an alternative to operations from laparotomy access, interventions on extrahepatic bile ducts using endovideoscopic technologies are of great interest. The latest technologies, materials, and methods used in laparoscopic surgery make it possible to achieve impressive results in the treatment of patients with choledocholithiasis and stenosing duodenal papillitis. An important role is also played by the tangible economic effect obtained by using laparoscopic techniques as a one-stage treatment of complicated forms of gallstone disease.

The purpose of the study. The main purpose of this study is to improve the results of treatment of patients with choledocholithiasis, stenosing duodenal papillitis and their combination by introducing and improving methods of laparoscopic interventions on extrahepatic bile ducts.

Research materials and methods. Research was carried out in the surgical departments of the Andijan branch of the scientific center of Emergency Medicine of the Republic, in the Department of Neurosurgery of the adti clinic, in the private clinic of Carona MEDLAIN.

The main group included 55 patients who underwent surgery from January 2020 to June 2023. In this group, a two - stage treatment of choledocholithiasis is mainly used-endoscopic transpapillary lith extraction, followed by laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Laparotomy is performed choledocholithomia if it is not possible to eliminate choledocholithiasis using endoscopic transpapillary interventions. Laparoscopic methods of treating cholelithiasis patients with choledocholithiasis and duodenal papillitis with stenosis are actively being introduced and improved to practice.

The results of the study. During 2018-2023, the prevalence of cholelithiasis and its complex forms has been shown. By population of 1,000 of Andijan region. From the tables presented, it can be seen that during this period the prevalence of cholelithiasis increased from 1,804 people per 1,000 inhabitants to 2,701 people per 1,000 inhabitants of the region, i.e. 49.7%. A similar trend is observed among other complications of gallstone disease. Thus, the prevalence of

choledocholithiasis rose from 0.235 to 0.347 per 1000 inhabitants, viz. By 47.7%, choledocholithiasis in combination with SDP is 0.155 to 0.193 (24.5%), choledocholithiasis-free SDP is 0.105 to 0.122 (16.2%) per 1000 people, and obstructive jaundice is 0.3 to 0.347, a complication of these diseases. per 1,000 inhabitants (34.8 percent) of the municipality's population.

The structure of operative activity is indicated for various nosological forms of cholelithiasis. For the period from 2012 to 2017. 12,526 cholecystectomies were performed in Andijan region. Table 11 shows that the leading place among all operations in cholelithiasis is occupied by laparoscopic cholecystectomy - this is 89.1% of the total number of cholecystectomies.

Conclusion. All patients are statistically divided into 2 homogeneous groups. The core group of 55 consisted of patients who underwent laparoscopic surgery. Patients in the 60-person control group underwent laparotomy surgery. In the first group, a promising analysis of the direct results of treatment, in the second Group, A Retrospective Analysis of the results of treatment of patients with choledocholithiasis, stenosis duodenal papillitis and a combination of them was carried out on the basis of medical data.